

**MATERIAL SOURCES FOUND IN THE ZOROASTRIAN TEMPLE OF
ZARTEPA IN THE URGUT REGION.**

**МАТЕРИАЛЬНЫЕ ИСТОЧНИКИ, НАЙДЕННЫЕ В
ЗОРОАСТРИЙСКОМ ХРАМЕ ЗАРТЕПА В УРГУТСКОМ РАЙОНЕ.**

UDC:72.03

Alikulova Gavhar

Maxmudova Nargiza

Samarqand state Institute of Architecture and Contruction
(Samarkand Uzbekistan)

Annotation.

This article presents data obtained as a result of the study and analysis of material sources found in the Zoroastrian temple of Zartepa in the Urgut region, and archaeological excavations carried out in the Christian temple of Southern Sogd in Nakhshab and the Urgut region.

Аннотация.

В данной статье представлены данные, полученные в результате изучения и анализа материальных источников, обнаруженных в зороастрийском храме Зартепа в Ургутском районе, и археологических раскопок, проведенных в христианском храме Южного Согда в Нахшабе и Ургутском районе.

Ключевые слова: Инфраструктура, материальные ресурсы, археология, туризм, христианская церковь, Согд, архитектурные сооружения национальной, иностранные инвестиции, регион.

Key words: Infrastructure, material resources, archeology, tourism, Christian church, Sughd region, national architectural structures, foreign investments, region.

The wide dissemination of information obtained as a result of the study and analysis of material sources found in the Zartepa temple of Jartepa, Urgut region,

serves to enrich the ideas of our people about the religions that existed in the early Middle Ages in our country.

Archaeological excavations of Christian churches in the southern Sogd and Urgut regions revealed the existence of the principles of religious tolerance in the early Middle Ages. The existence of Christianity and related churches in Central Asia, especially in Sogdiana, is reflected both in archaeological research and in written sources. In particular, Christian churches were opened on Registan Square, in Koshtepe near the village of Otamas in the Urgut region, in Koshtepe in Sufiyon and Nasaf.

The monument to Kushtepe I in the Urgut district of the Samarkand region is one of the buildings where Christianity is practiced and dates back to the 7th-8th centuries. The architectural features of the building are close to Byzantine Christian churches, and on the surface of the khum found here, baptismal rites are depicted. These data indicate that the Urgut region was the largest Christian center in Central Asia for several centuries.

Subsequent studies showed that Christian villages also existed in the ancient Nakhshab oasis. Scientific research in the field of the history of Christianity in Sogd (Russian mosque in the village of Sufiyon, Urgut region, Koshtepa temple in the village of Otamas, church on Registan Square). Ancient religious beliefs disappeared in the areas where Islam took hold, including the ancient Sughd region.

There are different views on the origin of the toponym Urgut. The famous orientalist V.L. Vyatkin noted that since the reign of the Mangyts, the village of Arkut, which is mentioned in historical documents, began to be called Urgut.

Based on ancient sources, it has been proved that Urgut is a sacred place with a 100000-year history. This is evidenced by ancient settlements and shrines in the area. Urgut differs from other areas in its unique national traditions, crafts and ethnographic features.

This is a very attractive feature for local and foreign travelers. The area has all the conditions for a calm, relaxing and fun holiday for tourists. The transport network is well developed, which allows them to comfortably travel to places of

travel and recreation. Based on ancient sources, it has been proven that Urgut is a sacred place with a history of 100 thousand years. This is evidenced by ancient settlements and sacred places in the region. Urgut differs from other regions with its unique national traditions, folk crafts and ethnographic features.

Many events related to the history of the peoples of the world took place on the territory of the Urgut region. In the spring of 329 BC. Alexander's army crossed the Hindu Kush mountains and invaded Central Asia. Greco-Macedonian troops occupied Marakand-Samarkand. According to the ancient historian Arrian, having arrived in Samarkand, in the spring of 327 they moved to the "Sogdian rocks". The fact that the fortress, known in history as the Sogdian Rocks, is located on a mountain causes controversy among many historians, and an unequivocal conclusion has not yet been made. However, it is clear that these rocks were located in the Urgut mountains.

On such a hill in the Urgut district is the village of Vagashti. The villagers speak Tajik. According to toponymist S. Karaev, the original name of this village in historical books was called Vakhshivar. The fact is that the name of the Greek-Macedonian commander does not coincide with the name of the village. Even now, about 10-1 o'clock in the upper part of the village, the place of the fortress was preserved, and it is natural that the Urgut region was also oppressed by the Greek-Macedonian invaders.

In the same year, traces of ancient settlements were discovered in Urgut on the Tashkent-Termez road in places called Shokhaksa, Takaliksa, Yumalatmasa. The discovery of primitive people in Omonkoton is of great interest to scientists. For this reason, in 1953-1954, all foothill villages and existing caves in the mountains of the Urgut region were carefully studied.

This is a very attractive feature for domestic and foreign travelers. The area has all the conditions for a quiet, relaxing and fun holiday for tourists. The transport network is well developed for convenient movement in tourist and recreational areas.

LITERATURE

1. Akhmedov M.K. "History of Central Asian Architecture" Tashkent 1995.
2. Saodat Pulkanova. "Samarkand: truth and myths about holy places" Khujand 2014.
3. Abdurashid Abdurakhmonov. "Urgut History and Literature" Uzbekistan "Fan" Publishing House 1990.
4. D.A. Nozilov "Folk Architecture". Tashkent Science, 1982.